

ORGANIZATIONAL STRATEGIES, CHANGE MANAGEMENT PRACTICES, AND MOTIVATION ON NURSES' COMMITMENT

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10963793>

ABSTRACT

This study investigated the extent of organizational strategies, change management practices, and level of motivation with which fit best in improving nurses' commitment. It utilized a descriptive correlational method among 344 nurses in Department of Health accredited hospitals in Sarangani Province and General Santos City. A self-made survey questionnaire was developed, validated, and administered to the respondents. Weighted mean was used to analyze the extent of implementation of organizational strategies, change management practices, and level of motivation and commitment. Spearman correlation was used to determine the relationships of the independent variables and the dependent variable; while multiple linear regression was utilized to determine the relationship of the independent variables to the dependent variable. Results showed that organizational strategies ($r=0.355$) ($\text{sig}=0.000$), change management practices with a correlation value of $r = 0.164$ ($\text{sig.}=0.002$), and motivation $r=\text{value of } .214$ ($\text{sig.}=0.000$) showed a significant relationship with commitment. All identified variables, namely, organizational strategies, change management practices, and motivation, significantly

influenced nurses' commitment. The work of being a nurse and the mission itself appeared to be where most of the nurses' commitment stems and comes from. This may explain why nurses still find nursing a fulfilling, rewarding, and satisfying profession. The result led to the recommendation to consider the proposed development program to be implemented which is relevant and timely in addressing the concern in increasing nurses' commitment.

Keywords: *Nurses Commitment, Organizational Strategies, Change Management Practices, Motivation*

INTRODUCTION

In the present-day environment, organizations are facing new challenges in creating a committed workforce (Andrew, 2017 & Bucăța, 2018). Further, Bucăța (2018) said that no organization can perform at peak levels unless each employee is committed to the organizational objectives.

Coronavirus Disease - The 2019 pandemic posed numerous adverse consequences like economic crises, global health shocks, changes in social behaviors, and challenges affecting the organization level from top to bottom. It also created disruption, uncertainty, complexity, and ambiguity in all organizations. With these challenges, Azizi et al. (2021) emphasized that people are the primary asset of any organization and that help achieve organizational goals. Accordingly, to manage human resources sustainably, studying commitment is significant.

According to Indradevi and Veronica (2018), commitment is generally characterized as the relative strength of an individual's identification with and involvement in a particular organization. Further, Jawaad et al. (2019) argued that Human Resource Management (HRM) has the capacity to influence the organizational conduct and behavior of the employees, thereby ensuring the achievement of the corporate goals and objectives. Human Resource Management positively influences firm performance which leads to commitment. Further, HRM practices are critical in the execution of effective training for

the employees, enhancing their inspiration through compelling reward strategies and reinforcing the enrollment and determination process.

Decades of commitment studies have taken place, and despite considerable advances, the field is currently working towards understanding workplace commitment. The field has been separated and divided in its fundamental understanding, as cited by Rosenberg et al. (2018). Despite this, there are a few studies focusing extensively on how nurses actually perform their jobs and concepts such as nurses' commitment and job performance. Further, most studies are focused on the relationship between organizational commitment and job performance (Lincoln et al., 2019).

To date, no study has investigated the influence of organizational strategies, change management practices, and motivation with which fits best in improving nurses' commitment. Further, professional development through an employee development program is critical to the nursing profession because it emphasizes the importance of human resource development, continuing education, and upholding competency.

On the other hand, the Philippines is facing challenges in the Filipino nursing workplace, including staffing concerns, operational mishaps and problems, generational gaps among nurses, high nurse turnover, and patient handling issues (Ramelb-olivar, 2016). These situations have greatly affected nurses' commitment. Without a sufficient number of committed nurses, the quality and safety of the healthcare system will be jeopardized. Being an important concept in human resource management, a wide span of literature exists on employee commitment research. Nonetheless, Fabiene and Kachchhap (2016) argued that little is known about the factors that enhance employee commitment among healthcare professionals in the Philippines.

At present, the governor of the Philippine Nurses Association - Region XII said that nurses' commitment to their profession was tested during this time of the pandemic. Moreover, there is a nursing shortage globally, and hospitals have sought many ways to increase nurses' commitment to organizations. However, the strategies have been only partially successful because they are based on a narrow conceptualization of commitment that fails to take into account nurses' views and participation in organizational development, as well as looming challenges on unequal pay and benefits, retirement and hospitalization benefits, and workplace safety.

With these realities, the researcher was interested in studying the commitment of nurses in terms of employee engagement, job satisfaction, and career development. The researcher was also interested in investigating organizational strategies' influence on goal setting and visioning, human resource management practices, operational excellence, and corporate culture. Further, the researcher considered the extent of change management practices in terms of leadership, communication, and development programs. Additionally, the researcher was interested in determining the level of motivation in terms of work environment, compensation, promotion, and rewards and resources.

Understanding what factors contributed to the commitment of nurses was essential to developing strategies and focus that could close the gap and ensure involvement and productivity for nurses. As such, this study explored the influence, if any, between organizational strategies, change management practices, and motivation on nurses' commitment, which led to crafting a development program for nurses in hospitals and other healthcare facilities.

Conceptual Framework

The conceptual framework of this study was presented in Figure 1. The framework showed the relationship between the independent and dependent variables. The independent variables include organizational strategies, change management practices, and motivation, while nurses' commitment as the dependent variable.

The extent of implementation of organizational strategies in the hospital was determined through goal setting and visioning, human resource management practices, operational excellence, and corporate culture. According to Gupta (2011), organizational strategy is a dynamic long-term plan that maps the route toward the realization of the organization's goals and vision, and factors such as the organization's corporate culture impact a company's ability to carry out objectives and plans. Likewise, human resources management practices as part of the systems and processes that are expected to be consistent with organizational strategy (Rao & Krishna, 2015). Furthermore, Babalola and Nwanzu (2020) cited Treacy and Wiersema's 1995 model that includes operational excellence as one factor influencing organizational strategies.

Change management practices were studied based on the following constraints: leadership, communication, and development programs. As emphasized by Roberts (2017), it was found that transformational leadership style, organizational change readiness, and effective communication are three major key factors that influence successful organizational change as well as employee development that goes a long way in training, sharpening the skills of an employee, and upgrading his/her existing knowledge and abilities.

The level of motivation was measured using the following factors namely, work

Figure 1. Conceptual Framework

environment, compensation, promotion and rewards, and resources. These variables were presumed to have an effect on the nurses' commitment. Work motivation, according to Joseph et al. (2017), consisted of both intrinsic and extrinsic motivation. It was influenced by many factors like organizational structure, monetary incentives like salaries, wages, bonuses, etc., benefits like housing, security, gratuities, medical aids, loans, and advancements, and psychological incentives like satisfaction, recognition, freedom to work, workgroup relations, etc. It also included dimensions like dependence, organizational orientation, workgroup relations, psychological incentives, material incentives, and job situations.

The dependent variable was the commitment of nurses. It included employee engagement, job satisfaction, and career development. Ahmad et al. (2020) cited that Brewer (1995) identified factors that affect nursing staff commitment, such as nurse identification, trust management, willingness to invest effort, participation in decision-making, voicing concern, feeling place of work was equitable, managerial strategies, and compliance. Further, they also cited that factors such as job satisfaction, work experience, and size of the organization influence commitment.

Related Literature

The following presents the related literature on organizational strategies, change management practices, motivation, and commitment of nurses.

Organizational Strategies

In today's scenario, most organizations struggle with implementing realistic strategies for growth. Leaders of organizations were faced with developing and implementing strategic plans that promote organizational effectiveness while addressing potential threats. Accordingly, the sum of the actions a company intends to take to achieve long-term goals defines organizational strategy. Collectively, these actions make up a company's strategic plan. Strategic plans require involvement from all levels of the department and it take at least a year to complete. In a step-by-step manner, the top management creates the larger organizational strategy, while middle and lower management adopt goals and plans to fulfill the overall strategy (Johnson, 2019).

According to Fenişer et al. (2017), the organizational strategy was described as a desirable image of the organization in the future and is designed to target what aims to make the organization. Strategic thinking is the key to achieving success in a competitive environment which is constantly changing. Also, Park (2015) said that an organizational strategy can impact employee commitment. Employee attitudes toward the organization's strategy are important factors in the success of an organizational strategy. Chubbs (2020) posited that organizational leaders should have the right strategy to sustain an organization. In many organizations today, the implementation of a new strategic plan became more responsive to a changing environment in meeting the needs of clients and workforce. Further, shared values are the foundation of an organization and organizational leaders are emphasizing this principle as they interact with stakeholders (Chubbs, 2020).

Goal setting and visioning

Organizational strategy according to Gupta (2011) was a dynamic long term plan that maps the route towards the realization of the organizations' goals and vision. Hence, in his study, one of the factors that should be considered is goal setting and visioning. Goals and objectives provide organizations with a blueprint that determines a course of action and aids them in preparing for future changes. A goal is a term characterized as a future state that an organization or individual strives to achieve. For each goal that an organization sets, it also sets objectives. An objective is a short-term target with measurable results. Without clearly-defined goals and objectives, organizations will have trouble coordinating activities and forecasting future events (Marler, 2012).

Further, Marler (2012) said that organizational goals serve four basic functions; they supply guidance and direction, facilitate planning, motivate and inspire employees, assist organizations, and evaluate and control performance. Organizational goals inform employees the direction of the organization and how it plans to get there. Employees who experience difficult decisions can refer to the organization's goals for guidance. Goals promote planning to determine how these will be met and achieved. To satisfy a need, employees set and prioritize goals in order; hence, goals can be motivational and these increase performance. Control and evaluation help organization to counter check and compare its actual performance to its goals and then make any necessary adjustments. Gartenstein (2019) further emphasized that useful goals should be challenging and

achievable. He further said that to be truly useful, goals should also be clear and – whenever possible – quantifiable.

Pyšný and Zrůst (2014) argued that management theoreticians agree that goal is one of the important factors of consciously managed companies. However, for the staff and management perceived importance of goals for various corporate levels is different. As far as the organization has a clear vision and goal, employees know the way. It serves as the engine of an organization, which not only motivates but also activates staff, managers, and stockholders.

Human resource management practices

Human resources management practices, as emphasized by Rao and Krishna (2015), are part of the systems and processes that are expected to be consistent with organizational strategy. It is presumed that human resource policies and practices influence employee behavior. If different employee behaviors are required to implement different strategies, then human resource policies and practices should systematically vary with organizational strategy. Further, Al Adresi and Darun (2017) cited that employees, with the help of organizational support, will be able to contribute to enhancing organizational commitment. Managers of organizations must personally lead the process of strategic implementation and performance of strategic human resource management practices. Also, the researchers emphasized that organizations should prioritize good human resource management practices as a planned approach in order to establish an open, flexible, and caring management style.

Operational excellence

Babalola and Nwanzu (2020) cited Treacy and Wiersema's 1995 model that includes operational excellence as one of the factors that influence organizational strategies. Similarly, according to Moran (2014), operational excellence is an opportunity-driven improvement program that identifies opportunities to safely and sustainably increase the value of business. It also reduces risk and lost opportunity in a value-prioritized sequence. Furthermore, operational excellence is a high-performance, cooperative, success-oriented work culture that elevates mindset, actions, and activities to create the superior sustainable value safely. It requires thinking well beyond accelerating efficiency to improving effectiveness.

Corporate culture

Gupta (2011) argued that behaviors that are supposed to achieve strategic goals may be supported or impeded by culture. As he cited the study of Schwartz and Davis (1981), they pointed out, for better or worse, corporate culture has a leading impact on a company's ability to carry out objectives and plans, especially when a company is shifting its strategic direction.

Corporate culture can influence economic gains and outcomes, such as an organization's effectiveness and value creation (Fiordelisi et al., (2019). Zhao et al. (2018) expressed that corporate culture can benefit performance through three channels: enhanced coordination and control within the firm, improved goal alignment between the firm and its members, and increased employee effort. Corporate culture improves efficiency in an organization by enhancing coordination and control within the firm. It helps employees to interact and engage with each other. Additionally, it can develop employees' commitment to firms by enhancing their bond with the firm.

A promoted corporate culture collectively motivates employees to work toward corporate goals and thus increases firm value and financial performance. However, shareholders may not value corporate culture promotion, regarding it as an avoidable expense, which can lead to decreased firm value. Furthermore, a bad culture can be an obstacle to reaping benefits for firms (Zhao et al., 2018).

Change Management Practices

Change management is one of the biggest challenges in today's era. The prerequisite for the growth, development, and survival of any organization is to merge internal and external changes. Hence, along with other important business units of an organization, HR also needs to take the lead in keeping up with the required pace (Nasir, 2017).

Organizations must constantly innovate and embrace new ideas and ways of working to retain their competitiveness and survive (Belias & Koustelios, 2014). Change and its management have attracted much attention over the years, as evidenced by the many books, research papers, and dissertations on the subject. For example, a search of academic literature in 2017 using the keyword 'change' in PsycINFO resulted in

48,879,883 items. Despite the abundance of material, many change initiatives fail (Pieterse et al., 2012).

As emphasized by Roberts (2017), it was found that transformational leadership style, organizational change readiness, and effective communication are three major key factors that influence successful organizational change. He said that transformational leaders create and provide a vision for change and maintain relationships with followers. More so, organizational readiness involves development programs like planning, developing strategies, and implementing change. Generally, readiness impacts employees' commitment, beliefs, attitudes, and intentions toward change. In addition, communication provides clarity and direction and enforces commitment to change.

Leadership

Akinbode and Al Shuhumi (2018) said that to manage change successfully, an organization needs skillful and effective leaders. These leaders, on the other hand, need to understand the change management process. They also need to equip themselves with appropriate leadership styles and traits so that these leaders are able to initiate and guide the change process successfully.

According to Frisina (2014), leaders in an organization make things happen. Influential leaders go a step further by making a positive impact and difference in organizations and the lives of people who serve and are served by the organization. In a similar view, Frisina (2014) cited that influential leaders who act at a higher level, are more productive, and achieve greater results than other leaders with similar circumstances and resources. It is notable that influential leadership reveals how good people skills—trust and accountability, not processes—can strengthen the organization's pursuit of performance excellence as well as how leaders and staff will change their behavior when they understand how it affects the outcome of their work, the lives of those around them, and the organization's over-all performance.

Communication

More so, Heathfield (2019) said that no organization exists in which employees are completely happy with communication. Communication is one of the pressing issues in

organizations. It is an aspect most frequently complained about by most employees during organizational change and daily operations. Effective communication requires four interworking components to create shared meaning, a favorite definition of communication. The individual sending the message should present the message clearly and radiate integrity and authenticity. The person receiving the message must decide to listen, ask questions for clarity, and trust the sender of the message. The delivery method chosen must suit the circumstances and the needs of both the sender and the receiver. The content of the message has to resonate and connect on some level with the already-held beliefs of the receiver (the employee). It should include the information that the employee wants to hear and must answer the employee's questions.

Schulz-Knappe et al. (2019) found that the higher employees perceived the quality of information about the change, the lower their resistance. He also posited that commitment describes how much employees identify with their employer and how willing they are to engage with the organization. In fact, several studies have shown that employees with higher job satisfaction and higher commitment have a greater willingness to participate in change processes (Schulz-Knappe et al., 2019).

Development programs

Individuals in an organization form its vital resource and must be valued, nurtured and retained. Juneja (2019) cited that employees are the most valuable assets and truly the backbone of an organization. Every employee, in his/her own way, contributes towards the success or failure of an organization. Without employees in an organization, even the most powerful machinery with the latest technology would not function. Employee development is a joint initiative of the employee and the employer to upgrade an individual's existing skills and knowledge. It is of utmost importance for employees to keep themselves abreast with the latest developments in the industry to survive the fierce competition.

Moreover, employee development goes a long way in training, sharpening an employee's skills, and upgrading his/her existing knowledge and abilities. In layman's language, employee development helps develop and nurture employees so that they become reliable resources and eventually benefit the organization. Employees also develop a

sense of attachment to the organization as a result of employee development activities (Juneja, 2019).

Towns (2019) in his study argued that development programs increase employee satisfaction and are significant in an employee's decision to stay with the company. Organizations have set up their employee development programs in a variety of ways. He contended that a truly effective development program should include learning, career planning, goal setting, and evaluation to implement change among employees and the organization successfully. These areas will help the program be beneficial to the employees who utilize it and to the organization that provides it.

Motivation

Perreira (2016) emphasized that work motivation has been associated with work productivity. In health care, low motivation levels are directly linked to low productivity, poor performance, decreased patient safety, and poor quality care. Further, hospital nurses are at the spearhead of services, directly in contact with patients twenty-four hours a day and nurses' performance is a key factor to be considered by all hospitals (Raden et al., 2019).

In addition, one of the functions of motivation is the degree of commitment and performance. Accordingly, motivating employees to execute tasks assigned to them is one of the major problems confronting management and managers. Motivation is one of the many factors affecting an employee's performance. Though motivation is a factor that influences a worker's performance, it is in short supply and needs to be constantly replenished (Teryima et al., 2016).

Work motivation can be characterized as the process by which behavior is energized, directed, and sustained in any organizational setting. It is a set of energetic forces that spring up both within and beyond an individual's being to initiate work-related behavior and influence its form, direction, intensity, and duration. Work motivation consists of both intrinsic and extrinsic motivation. It is influenced by many factors like organizational structure, monetary incentives like salaries, wages, bonuses, etc., benefits like housing, security, gratuities, medical aids, loans, and advancements, and psychological incentives like satisfaction, recognition, freedom to work, workgroup relations, etc. It also includes

dimensions like dependence, organizational orientation, workgroup relations, psychological incentives, material incentives, and job situations (Joseph et al., 2017).

Potgieter and Tait (2013) cited the complexity of the relationship between work motivation, performance, and productivity in which hygiene factors, such as job satisfaction, rewards, leadership styles, and communication, contribute to work performance and productivity of employees. Employee skills, training, availability of resources, management practices, and economic conditions also influence employee performance.

The health sector is defined as labor-intensive, and the strength of an organization that operates within its context is inextricably linked to the level of employee performance (Kitsios & Kamariotou, 2021). Therefore, it is essential to take maximum advantage of the full potential of human resources by providing the appropriate incentives, which will naturally cause the adoption of the desired attitude and behavior.

According to Kitsios and Kamariotou (2021), factors that contribute to the increase in staff satisfaction are salary and wages, leadership, rewards, meritocracy, objective judgment on promotions and salary increases, rational division of duties and work within the unit, fair distribution of shifts and impartial attitude of the administration. Moreover, employees are highly satisfied with their jobs when there are opportunities for development and growth within the health unit.

Schopman et al. (2015) cited that the existence of comfortable and functional workplaces and staff rest, the existence of appropriate equipment and consumables, and the relationships among employees and those between employees with management affect the commitment of nursing and medical staff.

Work environment

AbuAlRub et al.'s (2016) study results necessitate improving workplace conditions among nurses in underserved areas. The findings also emphasized the positive impact of a supportive work environment on enhancing nurses' intention to stay or retain at work.

One of the many challenges for a business, as cited by Raziq and Maulabakhsh (2015), is to satisfy its employees to cope with the ever-changing and evolving environment, achieve success, and remain in competition. More so, in order to increase the efficiency, effectiveness, productivity, and job commitment of employees, the management should focus on strategies that create an effective workplace environment. They also argued that an organization needs to pay attention to creating a work environment that enhances the ability of employees to become more productive in order to increase profits for the organization.

Chandrasekar (2011) also affirmed that unhealthy and unsafe work environments in terms of poor ventilation, immoderate noise, inadequate lighting, etc., affect employees' productivity and health.

Compensation

According to Ali and Ahmad (2017), pay is considered a monetary and extrinsic reward, including salary, bonus, cost of living allowance, etc. Pay should be equal to the work an individual does. If pay is not perceived to be equal to the workload, it leads to dissatisfaction, and the employee's motivation level is affected. Pay based on performance will produce more promising results in terms of employee productivity and job satisfaction.

These findings in the study of Chen et al. (2015) state that Chinese nurses' work attitudes are influenced by their satisfaction with pay and their satisfaction with the psychological rewards they receive from their head nurse. When nurses feel satisfied with both types of rewards, they have a lower turnover intention and higher levels of job satisfaction and affective organizational commitment. Hospital managers should prioritize financial and psychological rewards to develop an efficient reward system to attract, motivate, and retain qualified nurses.

Strategically targeted compensation practices can be used to advance specific important organizational goals. Embracing the adage "you get what you pay for," nurse leaders and their organizations have a strategic opportunity to strengthen and transform their nursing staff and leadership teams through creative design and application of pay practices. Healthcare employers can leverage their compensation program through staff

communication to build loyalty, trust, and engagement within their nursing workforce. Bedside nurses frequently do not understand the intricacies of how they are paid and incentivized through their employer's pay practices. Seasoned nurse leaders know that nurse satisfaction with pay is frequently one of the lowest-rated and most intractable variables on employee engagement surveys. The influence of pay can be a neglected variable in reports focused on nurse turnover and nurse staffing. Through collaboration and shared decision-making, senior nurse leaders can ensure that their compensation strategy supports the values and development of their professional nursing staff and ensures financial viability for their organization. Nursing compensation practices have remained stable and consistent across hospital employers within geographical markets and throughout the United States (Bradley, 2021).

Promotion and rewards

Ali and Ahmad (2017) said that rewards and recognition have a prominent impact on job satisfaction of employees. The human resource department should guarantee that while setting the strategies for the rewards and recognition they should keep equality in mind for the best outcomes in terms of high productivity and performance. Proper market analysis should also be done as to how other organizations are working on the satisfaction of their employees.

Furthermore, promotion in the study of Ali and Ahmad (2017) means climbing the corporate ladder, or in other words, when an individual moves from one designation to a higher one, it is considered as promotion. Promoting employees to improve job satisfaction can be challenging for HR managers unless there is justification that promotions will resolve job satisfaction issues. Pay and promotion are part of extrinsic rewards, which are monetary.

According to Shanafelt and Noseworthy's (2017) study, people can be motivated by rewards. Many healthcare organizations have linked physicians' financial compensation to productivity to harness this principle. In some settings, physicians' income is entirely based on productivity, and in others, it is structured as a base salary with a productivity bonus.

Resources

Aside from the acknowledgment of their work, employees are highly satisfied with their job when there are opportunities for development and growth within the health unit (Schopman et al., 2015). To determine the importance of motivating health workers in Sweden, Holmberg et al. (2015) investigated the factors that can motivate nurses. They argued that nurses cannot be motivated only by material or financial rewards but also by factors contributing to their personal and professional development. They also argued that their motivating factor is the job satisfaction they receive both from the execution of their responsibilities and from the conditions prevailing in their work environment.

Commitment

Organizations value commitment among their employees to reduce withdrawal behavior, such as lateness, absenteeism, and turnover. Therefore, these values appear to have potentially serious consequences on overall organizational performance. Commitment reflects the feelings of dependency, identity, loyalty, and desire to continuously stay within an organization to achieve a goal (Womack et al., 2018).

Commitment is characterized generally as the relative strength of an individual's identification with and involvement in a particular organization. It can be characterized by at least three related dimensions: a strong belief in and acceptance of the organization's goals and values, a willingness to exert considerable effort on behalf of the organization, and a strong desire to maintain membership in the organization (Indradevi & Veronica, 2018).

Employee commitment is one of the important factors that facilitates successful strategy implementation. To implement strategies successfully, firms need to create an organizational climate that supports the commitment of employees to strategy implementation. Employee commitment is necessary to align strategy implementation and strategy decisions. Employee involvement and commitment are key to implementing successful strategic change in organizations. Commitment increases employee motivation, shortens the lead time required for strategy implementation, and allows fast responses to changes in the business environment. Empirically, many researchers have

examined the impact of strategy implementation and performance (Kumar, 2015; Aremu & Oyinloye, 2014; Ibrahim et al., 2012).

According to Gul (2015), the psychological immersion of an employee with his institute through a sense of belonging, ownership of organizational goals, and being ready to accept challenges defines commitment. It will become difficult for an organization to achieve strategic goals without workplace commitment. Organizational commitment means the engagement of an employee to perform his work with eagerness and excitement. The commitment level of employees is directly related to the performance of an organization. Committed employees will be able to accomplish their jobs more than management expectations. High-level commitment from workers is indispensable for accelerating output and obtaining sustainable competitive advantages (Nadia & Fathurahman, 2017).

High commitment is viewed as central to positive employee relations. It also has important consequences in health service organizations, as it has a major role to play in delivering high-quality health care. Patient care and satisfaction are directly correlated with the contribution of direct care (McCabe & Garavan, 2011). Common to all the conceptualizations of commitment found in the literature is a link with turnover, although the nature of that link differs. Employees who are strongly committed are those who are least likely to leave the organization (Aluwihare-Samaranayake et al., 2018). Furthermore, Aluwihare-Samaranayake et al. (2018) argued that healthcare organizations are social institutions that depend on nurses to provide direct service to patients. Retention of nurses by the healthcare organization that employs them is crucial to future delivery of healthcare. One potential solution to turnover is a better understanding of the major factors associated with or modifying nurses' commitment to their work. Research on organizational commitment is important to healthcare institutions striving for a competitive advantage. Nurses work long hours and experience frequent shift changes and other unique stressors, such as threats to personal safety. Nurses require autonomous, independent decision-making in direct patient care, all for a modest amount of pay. Many nurses, however, persist in hospitals despite such hardships. Why nurses continue or leave may be explained in part by the commitment they feel towards their immediate work environment including their patients, families, profession, community, or country. The phenomenon of commitment is a cornerstone of human social life. Commitments make individuals' behavior predictable in the face of fluctuations in

their desires and interests, thereby facilitating the planning and coordination of joint actions involving multiple agents (Michael & Pacherie, 2015).

As emphasized by Nadia et al. (2017), there is a clear relationship between the work environment and the well-being of the individual both physically and psychologically so that a comfortable working environment can increase the sense of employee well-being. Employee well-being is one of the crucial issues for the organization, which deals with the mental health that happens in the workplace. Accordingly, medical workers are professionals who intensively experience job stress. Medical workers who work as doctors, nurses, therapists, and others have to deal with complaints of patients, their families, and illnesses, so they are very susceptible to depression. A stressful work environment can lead to several health symptoms that include physical health (such as cardiovascular and gastrointestinal problems), mental health (such as blood pressure, anxiety, and depression), and low job satisfaction. To provide maximum service to the patient, one important factor is the physical condition of an adequate working environment to help the work become easier, increase productivity, and increase employee well-being.

Wainwright (2018) said that committed employees bring added value to the organization through their determination, proactive support, relatively high productivity and awareness of quality. They display positive behavior within organizations, are more likely to positively refer the company to contacts, and are furthermore likely to adopt the organization's vision and goals (both professionally and personally). Also, they are much less likely to leave their current position in the workplace.

Ahmad et al. (2020) cited Brewer's (1995) identified factors affecting nursing staff commitment, such as nurse identification, trust management, showing a willingness to invest effort, participation in decision-making, voicing concern, feeling their place of work is equitable, managerial strategies, and compliance. Further, they also cited that factors such as job satisfaction, work experience, and size of the organization influence commitment.

Estigoy and Sulasula (2020) argued that in today's fast-paced competitive world, every organization constantly faces new challenges regarding sustained productivity and creating a committed workforce. Commitment in different forms displays that there are employees who choose to stay their whole life within the organization; there is a certain

abstract string that binds individuals to the organization; employees who are reactive if needed; and the factors found common to the employees that lead to commitment. Being feeling involved and engaged is a different thing as a whole to the organization. Committed employees are the organization's greatest assets, and they are believed to play a vibrant role in overall business efficiency and profitability.

Additionally, Estigoy and Sulasula (2020) said that commitment is a feeling of loyalty and oneness that an employee feels towards the organization. This is normally based on personal experiences with regard to the organization's policies and procedures and employees interaction serve as agent of the organization. The feelings and beliefs of employee for being part of the organization somewhat boost their productivity. Organizational Commitment is a core predictor of employee's attitude to the organization and is a strong indicator of turnover behavior, withdrawal tendency, and organizational citizenship behavior. The bond of the employee interprets what are the values and attitudes of employee. Committed employees are increasingly becoming a valued asset in organizations. Employee commitment is viewed as a commitment to the organization as well as employees' commitment to their occupations.

Employee engagement

Indradevi and Veronica (2018) emphasized that employee engagement is employees' emotional commitment to the company and its goals. So when employees are engaged and committed to the organization and its goal, they care about the hospital, their team, and their patients. There is a significant link between employee engagement and patient care and satisfaction improvements. For instance, higher nurse engagement scores lead to lower patient mortality and complications, according to a recent Gallup study. Just like employees in any other industry, healthcare providers will also do better work and provide better care if they are happy and committed in their jobs. Service Organizations such as hospitals are a social system that requires human resources for its effective and efficient operations. It is essential for hospitals to focus on their employees and keep them satisfied and committed to enhancing hospital efficiency in healthcare service delivery. With organizational commitment being seen as the main area of focus in human resource management, there is also a need to look into the employee's commitment to ensure employees' well-being, which will further drive organizational performance.

An employee's competency is a capability and characteristic owned by the employee in the form of knowledge, skills, and attitudes, and is required for completing the duties professionally, effectively, and efficiently (Aini, 2018). According to Sagherian et al. (2017), hospital nurses are expected to maintain optimal work performance, yet fatigue can threaten safe practice and result in unfavorable patient outcomes.

Job satisfaction

In order to attain a satisfactory level of organizational management in health institutions, one has to take into account employees' job satisfaction and organizational commitment. The fundamental paradigm of the relationship between job satisfaction and organizational commitment is that if an employee is satisfied with the job, he/she will develop a stronger commitment to the organization (Veličković et al., 2014).

Job satisfaction can be defined as how contented an employee is with his/her job. If the nature of work and the rewards given are both monetary and non-monetary and according to the expectations of an employee, he tends to be satisfied with his job. If not, it will result in a dissatisfied employee that might lead to an increase in turnover. Employee's productivity, and creativity increase when they are happy with their job because they become more attentive and display more dedication toward their specific work. Therefore, employee satisfaction plays an important role in organizational growth (Ali & Ahmad, 2017).

Moreover, job satisfaction, organizational commitment, level of education, experience, nurses' morale, work-related stress and burnout, support from co-workers, supportive supervision and feedback, training on clinical tools, recognition, job expectations, work environment, motivation, incentives, knowledge, skills, promotion, remuneration, and competency level are among the numerous factors affecting nurses' performance level. The recent data on nursing posts in the country informs that nurses make up the largest number of health workers in the public health sector. It only means that the country relies hardly on nurses for service delivery, and their performance is critical for the successful provision of health care (Tesfaye, et al., 2015).

Eliyana et al. (2019) cited that job satisfaction is characterized by how employees are satisfied with their work. Job satisfaction is a common behavior to work performance while

awards and achievements are given. Empirically, job satisfaction has a relationship with work performance. It is said that an organization with more satisfied employees tends to be more effective and productive.

Huning et al. (2020) affirmed that highly satisfied employees often remain with the organization. Their study showed that if an individual is experiencing positive relationships at work, they tend to have high job satisfaction. The study of Bennett and Hylton (2021) emphasized that a nurse tends to be satisfied with one's job and stays at one's organization when certain components of job satisfaction are satisfied. These components include the following: autonomy, the work itself, policies of the organization, salary, supervision, status, and the opportunity for promotion. It is further posited that a main variable that tends to contribute to the high retention of nurses is organizational commitment.

Career development

Tsai (2014) explored the relationship between learning organizations, internal marketing, and organizational commitment in hospitals. Based on the findings, the implementation of a learning organization and internal marketing is a strategy that enhances the employees' commitment to healthcare organizations. The learning organization is defined as the continuous upgrading of employees' competencies to improve patients' care and the quality of the service. Thus, in order to be competent, healthcare should be able to adapt the technological and environmental changes, continual education, and training. In fact, learning organization helps to improve employees' creativity and efficiency in the workplace. Internal marketing involves strategies for human resources management to encourage and motivate the employees for training and updates. Therefore, healthcare employees tend to remain committed to the organization when the management practices, promotes, and enhances personal development and improvement of employees' capabilities and performance.

Pathirana (2020) posited that organizations should support their employees by creating a career development culture and providing career support by the management, the outcome of which is increased career satisfaction and commitment. Delbari et al. (2020) found that among 331 participants in two Iranian universities, staff self-regulation positively and significantly affected individual, organizational, and environmental

productivity factors. Based on the results, educational institutions, especially universities, should allow their staff to exploit their full potential by reinforcing their self-regulation and increasing their commitment.

Related Studies

The following presents the related studies on organizational strategies, change management practices, motivation level, and commitment of nurses.

El Muksoud et al. (2021) conducted a study on “Leadership behaviors, organizational commitment and innovative work behaviors among nurses”. Among 100 staff nurses working at Belbeis General Hospital, results showed that the highest percentage of staff nurses had a positive perception of the leadership behavior where staff nurses choose to work with a leader using leadership behaviors that include pure vision, commitment to excellence, loyal to their staff nurses, willingness to inspire, communicate, and lead others to greater accomplishment. They also foster innovation and stress the value of appreciating and valuing staff nurses. Leadership behaviors and workplace environment have often been seen as a vital element and features of management that influence the level of commitment of employees within the organization and have the possibility to boost organization effectiveness, innovative work behaviors among staff nurses, job satisfaction, as well as a sense of confidence about problem-solving in order to achieve the organizational objectives.

Rajput et al. (2021) conducted a study entitled, “An inclusive systematic investigation of human resource management practice in harnessing human capital”. This study showed that when it comes to utilizing or harnessing human capital for any organization, it becomes very important to know the management science behind Human Resource Management. Intellectual capital, technology, globalization, profitability via expansion, and change are all major business problems that companies are presently experiencing. These problems require companies to collaborate to create new skills, and human resource management is in charge. It assists companies in addressing competitive difficulties by acting as a leader. Human Resource professionals have lost their stereotype of monitoring policies and enforcing rules. They are now held accountable for their employees’ engagement and dedication to the company and motivate people to participate and take ownership. It is no longer a relic of the past. It has evolved from a

little reactive image to a much larger canvas. The new management of human resources is triggered by bringing the organization's management together with the workers, resulting in a merger of the person's and the organization's reservoirs of knowledge, culminating in the joint victory of both. Global competitiveness may be accomplished not only by using updated technology and facilities but also by encouraging workers to adhere to international standards in an efficient and effective manner. Human resources specialists in every firm on the global stage have the goal to influence the business world; it is currently in a paradigm change, and its role as a support function, relied on to assist others and to recruit and dismiss from businesses, is quickly fading. Human resources are taking a proactive role in addressing globalization's issues. It brings about change, enhances people's abilities to learn and cooperate, and handles variety, ambiguity, and complexity. The study and comparison of the perceptions of corporate workers, management faculty, and management students in an effort to understand the role of HRM in developing national talent for global success.

Adkins-Provost (2020) conducted a study on "Scottish nonprofit mental health organizational strategies to commercialize innovative products and services." As revealed in the study, many nonprofit organization (NPO) leaders lack strategies to commercialize innovative products and services to secure funding and ensure financial stability. NPO leaders who do not overcome financial challenges could face organizational failure and the inability to attain their mission. Grounded in stakeholder theory, this qualitative, single case study aimed to explore strategies that Scottish nonprofit mental health organization leaders use to commercialize innovative products and services to secure funding and ensure financial stability. The study participants were 4 leaders at a single mental health organization in Scotland. Semistructured interviews, organizational documents, government data, public data, and information from the participant organization's website comprised the data collected for this study. Identification of themes occurred using Yin's 5-step thematic analysis process, whereas data assessment and organization scoring occurred using the Baldrige Performance Excellence Program criteria. Key themes that emerged from the analysis included effective strategic planning, effective financial management, ineffective commercialization strategy, positive work environment, and partially effective workforce development. A key recommendation for NPO leaders is to incorporate robust marketing as part of their strategy to commercialize products and services. Commercialization of mental health services and tools could result in positive social change by expanding available resources within Scotland's mental health

community and creating a revenue source that will allow the NPO to continue providing vital services to the community.

Ahmad et al. (2020) conducted a study entitled, "Factors affecting nursing staff commitment at General Hospitals in Damietta City". Based on the study, commitment represents a strong desire to maintain the nursing staff of an organization; it reflects the nursing staff's to achieve the organization's goals and values, a desire to stay with the organization, and a willingness to exert much effort into the organization. The aims was to assess the factors affecting nursing staff commitment at general hospitals in Damietta City. A descriptive design was utilized with a sample of 421 nursing staff working at all inpatient units at Damietta general hospitals. The study tool consisted of three parts; part (I) personal characteristics which included personal and job characteristics; part (II) Three-component organizational commitment questionnaire to measure types of nurses' commitment and the degree of nurses' commitment to their work; part (III) factors affecting nurse's commitment questionnaire to assess the factors affecting nurses' commitment at workplace. The results showed that more than two thirds (70.5%)of nursing staff had moderate total commitment. It revealed that the highest percentage among factors affecting commitment was feeling their place of work is equitable and the lowest one was for voice concern. Therefore, the study recommended an orientation program for new nurses to know the goals, policies, objectives, and regulations of the organization and evaluate the training needs of nursing staff periodically to develop their skills and information, regular meetings between hospital administrations, nursing administrator and nursing staff to express their concerns and opinions, and discuss their work problem and solve it.

Blakely (2020) conducted a study entitled "Leadership Strategies to achieve organizational excellence." The study indicated inadequate quality management tools and processes that lead to inefficient hospital operations and poor organizational performance. Community hospital leaders who fail to modify and improve operations and organizational performance risk negatively impacting patient care and profitability. The qualitative study intended to determine strategies community healthcare leaders use to use effective quality management approaches to better operations and achieve organizational excellence. The participants included five community healthcare leaders in the northeast United States who effectively used quality management approaches to improve operations and achieve organizational excellence. Five key strategies were

identified as a result of the study: quality management tools and techniques, data measurement and analysis for performance improvement, strategic planning, leadership engagement and sponsorship, employee engagement, and deliberative management of resources.

Chubbs (2020) conducted a study on “Healthcare organizational design strategies to improve performance.” Based on the research conducted, business leaders are exploring ways to improve organizational performance through organizational design, including reviewing their organization's structures. Grounded in McKinsey’s 7S framework, this qualitative single case study aimed to explore organizational design strategies healthcare leaders used to improve organizational performance. Participants were six leaders within a healthcare organization in Alberta, Canada, who successfully developed and implemented organizational design strategies to improve organizational performance. The data collection techniques included a review of internal and external documents, a reflective journal, and semistructured interviews. Methodological triangulation and thematic analysis to complete the data analysis were used. The data analysis resulted in six key themes: leadership impact on organizational design, stakeholder engagement, staff considerations, corporate structure, organizational design strategy, and system processes. A key recommendation is that organizational leaders should complete organizational design. Implications for social change include leaders using or adapting the study’s findings to implement organizational design strategies, improve organization performance, and ultimately affect higher quality services. In addition, improved performance and culture might create sustainability, which results in increased job security and enhanced quality of life for employees.

Ubas-Sumagasyay and Oducado (2020), in a study entitled “Perceived Competence and Transition Experience of New Graduate Filipino Nurses,” argued that recruitment and hiring of new graduate nurses is seen as a potential strategy to mitigate the problem of nurse shortage. However, previous studies disclosed that new graduate nurses are inadequately prepared to enter practice and experience transition difficulties. This study aimed to determine new graduate Filipino nurses' perceived competence and transition experience. Seventy-nine conveniently chosen new graduate nurses were surveyed in this descriptive cross-sectional research. Self-administered instruments were used to gather data. Descriptive statistics, Mann–Whitney U test, and Kruskal–Wallis test were the statistical tools employed. Results indicated that new graduate nurses had high self-

reported fundamental nursing skills ($M= 7.99$) and core competence ($M= 8.16$), although areas needing improvement were identified. There were no significant differences in the perceived competence based on the length of experience, year graduated, area of assignment, sex, type of school graduated, CPD participation, and hospital bed capacity ($p > .05$). The major difficulty experienced by new graduates during their transition was related to changes in role expectations (72.2%). Majority expressed the need for increased support during their transition (83.5%). The most satisfying aspects of their working environment were ongoing learning (81%) and peer support (74.7%), while the least satisfying was the negative nursing work environment (55.7%). New graduate nurses are equipped with the necessary nursing skills and core competencies. However, gaps and areas needing improvement should be addressed and supported to assist them in their transition to the world of professional nursing practice. Follow up, feedback, mentoring, and preceptorship are beneficial to enhance the competencies of new graduate nurses and facilitate their successful transition into the nursing workforce.

Udo (2020) conducted a study entitled “The Relationship of Involvement, commitment, and Productivity to job satisfaction of Nurses.” Results showed that nurses play a vital role in the healthcare industry. It is important to understand factors that shape their involvement and job satisfaction, leading to enhanced patient care and retention. It was unknown whether there is a relationship between involvement, commitment, productivity, and job satisfaction in nurses in acute care hospital settings. The correlational study aimed to examine the relationship between involvement, commitment, productivity, and job satisfaction in nurses in an acute care hospital setting in Northern California. Findings indicate as nurses’ productivity increases, so does their satisfaction. Practical implications include strategies to enhance acute care nurses’ productivity.

Sellers (2019) conducted a study entitled “Exploring Strategies Organizational Development and Change Managers Need to Improve Best Ethical Practices in an Organization.” Despite the best efforts of organizations to eradicate unethical behavior by members of the organization, the problem still exists. The public has demanded that organizations and lawmakers crack down on the issue to help identify standards for accountability despite an employee’s position. The interviews were conducted with 13 professionals from varying industries and backgrounds, from frontline employees to Human Resource executives. Three emerging themes were produced in the study: first, there are two sets of standards in an organization; second, there is a breakdown in

communication; third, employees are not aware of the organization's mission and vision statement; fourth, they are not aware of the chain of command; and lastly, training. The research has found that there are policies and regulations in place to divert unethical behavior in workplaces. The research highlights areas that need improvement, which can strengthen an organization's ethical atmosphere and protect employees when they are fully aware of how the organization works.

Okodogbe (2018) conducted a study on the “Relationship between human resources management practices and employee intention to leave healthcare organizations.” Results showed that human resource management practices (HRMPs) are critical components associated with employee satisfaction and turnover. HRMPs have been widely documented in the literature as being significantly related to employees’ intention to leave the healthcare organizations. The healthcare sector is understaffed, while the demands and health needs of the population continue to grow. As a result, employees’ turnover is a great problem that the healthcare organizations experience. The purpose of the non-experimental and correlational study was to examine the relationship between four HRMPs of highly selective staffing, extensive training, compensation policy, and empowerment and intention of employees to leave the selected Long Island, New York, healthcare organization. The guiding theoretical framework of the study was based on job satisfaction theory, which pertained to employee performance in the organizations, and the theory of engagement, which is related to employee commitment, satisfaction, and employees’ intention to leave healthcare organizations. Convenience sampling was used to recruit at least 152 participants from the targeted population. Four predictor variables were included in the calculation for an F test of multiple regression analysis. The study procedure was completed by providing a link to the selected sample participants, who were voluntarily required to fill out questionnaires. The results of the analysis revealed that the four HRMPs were predictors of employees’ intention to leave healthcare organizations. It was recommended that the staffing procedure, providing adequate training, beneficial compensation plan, and empowerment to the employees in the healthcare sector should be integrated into the strategic plans to sustain and improve the healthcare sector and the institution itself while curtailing employee turnover.

Garrett (2017) conducted a dissertation entitled “An Approach to Aligning leadership development with organizational strategy management.” The researcher investigated approaches that key informants and practitioners have used to successfully align

leadership development and strategy management. Six key findings surfaced from the conduct of the study regarding the alignment of leadership development with strategy management. Firstly, leadership development in organizations should be differentiated to fit varying roles, yet integrated throughout the organization through similar and shared competencies. Second, leadership development competencies should be connected to and leveraged within the organization's strategy management processes. Third, organizations should have a formal approach that aligns leadership development with the company's current strategic management objectives and where the company is going and headed. Fourth, leadership development competencies should be in consonance with the beliefs and behaviors of senior executives. Fifth, leadership development competencies should be linked to the organization's key results through a strategic framework. Lastly, developing leadership competencies that produce specific results was an ongoing process best achieved through action learning. Regardless of the business sector or size of the organization, the findings of this study emphasized that a successful approach to facilitating the alignment of leadership development with strategy management was an approach that incorporates leadership, communication, culture, teamwork, programs, and alignment: the components of organizational capital.

White (2019) conducted a study entitled, "Strategies for employee retention in nonprofit organizations." According to the study, low employee retention is one of the main challenges for managers and negatively impacts an organization's ability to survive and remain competitive. Using Herzberg's two-factor theory, the purpose of this multiple case study was to explore strategies nonprofit sector managers use to retain employees. The participants included four (4) managers from four (4) Illinois nonprofit organizations who implemented successful strategies for employee retention. Data were collected using semistructured, face-to-face interviews, company documents, and archival records. A thematic analysis was used to analyze the data, which revealed three (3) themes: employee engagement, workplace culture, and employee feedback. The implications for positive social change include the potential to benefit communities through improvements in unemployment rates and decreased levels of stress on families. Managers are responsible for maintaining that a strong workforce must attract, train, motivate, and retain employees. Employee engagement has been found to decrease when employees perceive the work environment to be threatening, unfair, ambiguous, or risky. Work environments consisting of adequate levels of supervisor support, organizational support, and good peer relationships will promote higher levels of employee engagement and

retention. This study's results may also benefit nonprofit organization employees through better work environments and encouragement of employee engagement.

Ioannidis et al. (2019) conducted a study entitled "Change Agents and internal communications in organizational networks." The study results showed that the adoption of change in organizational networks is conditioned by the engagement of the so-called "change agents" initiating "cascades of change" and by the internal communication among the network members. The researchers investigated how the dynamics of the adoption of change are influenced by the engagement policy of the change agents and by internal communication. The dynamics of change adoption are modeled by generalizing the discrete diffusion equation in order to incorporate both the engagement policies of the change agents and the internal communication rules. Results are obtained by simulating the solutions (change management scenario) on four (4) real organizational networks. Agents with high degrees (hubs) are found to be most suitable to act as change agents. However, the most suitable change agents are not always the senior employees. The adoption of change is much faster, if agents communicate with "local hubs", avoiding random contacts. Change agents feed the network members with "thin slices" of influence to avoid crossing the "confidence bound". A small increase in the size of "slices" results in a significant acceleration of the adoption of change. Also, the value of "planning" versus "no planning", is estimated in the context of Change Management.

Legaspi (2019), in the study entitled "A comparison of job satisfaction among Filipino nurses employed in the Philippines and overseas," showed that Filipino nurses employed both locally and overseas have an average level of general satisfaction. Both groups also showed a high degree of intrinsic satisfaction and an average degree of extrinsic satisfaction. No significant difference was found in the level of general, intrinsic, and extrinsic job satisfaction of locally and overseas-employed Filipino nurses. The study found that social service, an intrinsic factor, is the major motivating force behind job satisfaction. Workload, an extrinsic factor, is the most common problem encountered by both groups of nurses. Salary is one of the factors keeping Filipino nurses overseas satisfied, while it is also one of the factors causing dissatisfaction among locally employed nurses.

Another study was conducted by Lymon (2019) entitled, "An analysis of employee motivation after metamorphose, conglomerated public health care systems." Based on

the study, a global epidemic of metamorphosed, conglomerated health care systems changed the face of public health care organizations. The problem is that public healthcare organizations merge into new systems, but the culture of each merged organization has not been formed under the new system. Public administrators, healthcare workers, and the Department of Health and Human Services are affected when there are issues in healthcare behavioral practices and performance outcomes. The research found that employee motivation is hard to achieve when there are issues within the internal structure of a new system. Using Herzberg's motivation-hygiene and Tajfel and Turner's social identity theories as the foundation, this correlational study examined the statistical relationship between growth opportunities, organizational culture, monetary compensation, and employee motivation. Secondary data were used from a sample of 3,033 healthcare workers from two (2) English hospitals in the United Kingdom. The study's results concluded that growth opportunities, organizational culture, and monetary compensation significantly correlate with employee motivation.

Schenk (2019), in the study entitled "A group development program based on transformational leadership to improve team performance," posited that as reimbursement models move from volume-based to value-based, organizations increasingly depend on meeting patient outcome goals in order to achieve their budgetary targets. Leadership teams are a vital part of healthcare organizations, and their performance is crucial to overall performance. The organization of interest saw a group of strong individual leaders struggle with outcome production due, in part, to overall team dysfunction. Using available evidence-based assessment tools and resources, the project program was developed to deliver a year-long program outline focused on the precepts of transformational leadership, including a foundation of trust to improve professionalism, the ability to inspire, promote effective interpersonal relationships, and business competencies to drive positive change.

Bel et al. (2018) completed a study entitled "Managing Change: Communication, Managerial Style and Change in Organizations." The results of the study showed the interplay between communication, manager attributes, and the probability that an establishment successfully implements a significant change. Change requires both sufficiently strong advocacy and enough communication to help overcome inertia inside the firm, and posit that frequent communication can be costly, particularly with strong managers and in larger establishments. The theoretical predictions are consistent with

the study's empirical analysis wherein, utilizing uniquely detailed establishment-level data, the researchers found out that firm size, regular communication, and result-oriented managers are all positively associated with change. However, the use of frequent communication in firms that successfully implemented a significant change is moderated when managers tend to be strongly focused on results and in larger establishments. This suggests that organizations wishing to foster change should consider the interaction between manager attributes and communication protocols.

In the investigation by Labrague et al. (2018) entitled "Perceptions of Organizational Commitment and Turnover Intention among Rural Nurses in the Philippines: Implications for Nursing Management", it was revealed that the unrelenting migration trend of Filipino nurses to other countries has threatened the quality of patient care services in the country. Despite this trend, no studies have been identified examining nurses' organizational commitment and turnover intention among rural nurses in the Philippines. Two hundred nurses from nine rural hospitals in the Central Philippines were asked to participate in the study and 166 nurses responded (an 83% response rate). Findings revealed that Philippine nurses were moderately committed (3.13 ± 0.24) to and were undecided (2.42 ± 0.67) whether or not to leave their organization. Nurses' age ($P=0.006$), gender, ($t = -2.25$, $P=0.026$), education ($t = 2.38$, $P<0.001$), rank ($t = 4.38$, $P<0.001$), and work experience ($t = 2.18$, $P=0.031$) correlated significantly with organizational commitment, while nurses' age ($P=0.028$) and education ($t=1.99$, $P=0.048$) correlated significantly with turnover intention. An inverse relationship was identified between organizational commitment and turnover intention ($r=-0.22$, $P=0.005$). The findings of this study highlight the need for the formulation and implementation of interventions to promote life-long commitment in nurses and to reduce turnover rates.

As shown in Krishnan's (2018) study on "Organizational Change Readiness: Effects of Organizational Structure and Leadership Communication in Organizational Change." Similar to other financial organizations, life insurance institutions are dealing with changes caused by the aging of the American population and technological advances. In addition, they are dealing with changes in the cultural and economic environment. Since multiple organizational change processes have failed to achieve the desired result, the topic of organizational change readiness needs to be addressed. This dissertation looks into organizational change models to identify the factors that help it embrace change—to be change-ready. This dissertation discusses the models of organizational change

preparedness and change readiness, focusing on organizational leaders' reaction to external environmental changes. The study found that organizational structure redesign and effective communication throughout the organization are two factors that assist with organizational change readiness. Using a systematic review of relevant literature and applying evidence-based research methodology, this dissertation found evidence supporting the arguments that organizational structural changes and effective communication assist leaders in making the desired changes that deliver the results they are looking for. This study focuses on specific factors within organizational change literature such as organizational change preparedness, organizational change readiness, organizational structural change, and the influence of effective leadership communication on organizational change.

Chiavoghi and Emerole (2017) conducted a study entitled, "Effects of Change Management on Employee Commitment – A Study of Selected Deposit Money Banks in Umuahia." This study examined the effect of change management on employee commitment to deposit money banks. A cross-sectional research survey was employed. The accessible population consists of ten (10) banks using a simple random sampling technique. A total of 122 staff were surveyed. Sample size is 93 using Taro Yamane. The validity of the instrument was ascertained using face validity. The reliability of the instrument was determined using the Cronbach alpha test. Spearman's Rank Order Correlation Coefficient (ρ) was used to test the hypotheses with the aid of SPSS (20.0). The study's findings revealed that change management has a positive significant effect on employee commitment. The study concluded that change management that is based on communication and employee participation will enhance employees' commitment in the organization. Firstly, it recommended that bank managers should adopt communication as a strategy to overcome resistance to change in the workplace. Secondly, managers of other financial institutions should encourage their employees to participate in the change management process.

Devera and Maniago (2017), in their study entitled, "Nurses' perceptions on professional practice environment and job satisfaction in select hospitals of Zambales, Philippines," which is a descriptive-survey study aimed to determine the perceptions of nurses on professional practice environment and job satisfaction in select hospitals in Zambales, Philippines. Research tools adopted from the Nurses' Work Index-R (Aiken and Patrician, 2000) and the Nurses' Job Satisfaction Scale (Yang et al., 2014) were utilized to gather

data from 180 hospital staff nurses. Results of the pilot study revealed that the internal content validity index was .974, and both professional practice environment ($\alpha=.943$) and nurses' job satisfaction ($\alpha=.830$) yielded a reliability coefficient greater than 0.70. Ethical clearance was properly secured prior to the distribution of survey questionnaires. The findings revealed that the respondents agreed to the aspects of professional practice environment (PPE) in their workplace, such as supportive management, nurses' involvement and acknowledgment of professionalism, quality of care and collaboration, and adequate resources. On the other hand, they were satisfied with the aspects of job satisfaction in terms of benefits and promotion, human relationships, workload, and job environment. Hospital management should maintain a supportive workplace that encourages nurses to remain in the health workforce and enables them to perform effectively. Moreover, promoting social relationships and interactions among nurses and other hospital personnel will enhance interpersonal relationships in the workplace. Cohesion, collaboration, and good communication with colleagues will assure quality care for patients. Thus, health policy-makers and managers must promote a sound professional practice environment.

Fernet et al. (2017) conducted a study entitled "Motivational Pathways of Occupational and Organizational Turnover Intention among Newly Registered Nurses in Canada." As findings showed, staff turnover is a major issue for healthcare systems. In a labor shortage, it is critical to understand the motivational factors underlying turnover intention in newly licensed nurses. Cross sectional data were collected from a sample of 572 French-Canadian newly registered nurses working in public healthcare in the province of Quebec, Canada. These results highlight the complexity of the motivational processes at play in the turnover intention of novice nurses, revealing distinct forms of commitment that explain how motivation quality is related simultaneously to the intention to quit the occupation and the organization. Healthcare organizations are advised to promote autonomous over controlled motivation in order to retain newly recruited nurses and sustain the future of the nursing workforce.

Gerbec (2017) conducted a study on "Safety change management – A new method for integrated management of organizational and technical changes." Research showed that changes are a daily reality in the process industry and potential implications on major accident hazards must be properly managed. Management of change is a part of safety management, however, changes are often complex and usually involve both technical

and organizational aspects. The researcher presented a new integrated method to make a distinction and named it a “Safety change management” to evaluate and manage change proposals, considering both technical and organizational dimensions in an integrated way. The plant managers involved found the proposed method detailed, effective, useful and transparent.

Lapeña et al. (2017) accomplished a study entitled “Transformational and Transactional Leadership Styles of Nurse Managers and Job Satisfaction among Filipino Nurses: A Pilot Study.” Based on the study collected from one hundred staff nurses in selected tertiary hospitals in Manila, it was found that Filipino nurses rated their level of satisfaction (M=3.37) from high to a moderate extent along with professional autonomy (M=3.91), work environment (M=3.81), work assignment (M=3.61), and benefits (M=2.71). Participants agreed that their nurse managers utilized either transformational or transactional leadership styles. Findings indicate that transformational ($r=0.558$, $p<0.000$) and transactional ($r=0.528$, $p<0.000$) leadership styles of nurse managers were correlated to nurses’ job satisfaction. The finding explicates that Filipino nurses were satisfied with their professional autonomy, work environment, and work assignment but moderately satisfied with work benefits, which were also apparent in the global literature. Furthermore, the results indicate that leadership styles are related to the overall job satisfaction of among nurses.

Roberts (2017) in his study entitled, “Factors that Influence Successful Organizational Change in Corporations: Examination of Change Management, employees’ Reaction to Change, and Change Outcomes” ascertained that corporations are confronted with two challenges today: the increasing demand for change in order to stay competitive and the implementation of successful organizational change. Although they usually bow to the demand for change, studies have found that more change initiatives fail to meet desired outcomes. Organizational change failure is often attributed to management style, employee reaction, and failure to integrate change outcomes. Organizational change is the process in which an institution changes its culture, operational methods, structure, strategies or technologies. This dissertation uses a systematic literature review to examine leadership style, employees’ reactions to change, and change outcomes management. The relationship between these three variables was examined in order to identify the factors that influence successful organizational change in corporations. It was found that transformational leadership style, organizational change readiness, and

effective communication are three key factors that influence successful organizational change. Transformational leaders create and provide a vision for change and maintain relationships with followers. Organizational readiness involves planning, developing strategies, and implementing change. Specifically, leadership and readiness impact employees' commitment, beliefs, attitudes, and intentions toward change. Communication provides clarity and direction and enforces commitment to change. In conclusion, the findings imply that a combination of leadership and managerial skills can lead to successful change management. An organization's preparation for change through effective communication with followers can influence successful organizational change.

Dones et al. (2016), in the study entitled "Working environment of nurses in the Philippines," posited that the work environment has been described as an important factor in the job satisfaction of nurses and the quality of service provided. However, little is known about the present work environment of Filipino nurses in the country. This study used a cross-sectional design to describe work environment variables affecting Filipino nurses, determine the degree of nurses' job satisfaction; and determine their intention to remain in their present work environment. A self-administered survey was developed by the study team and was distributed during the PNA national conference through the Chapter Presidents. This study discovered that the lowest positive responses were in the Physiologic and Safety Needs but despite this result, nurses reported high job satisfaction and intend to remain in their present work environment.

Lee and Raschke (2016), in the study entitled "Understanding employee motivation and organizational performance: Arguments for a set-theoretic Approach," said that empirical evidence demonstrates that motivated employees mean better organizational performance. The conceptual paper aims to articulate the progress made in understanding employee motivation and organizational performance and suggest how the theory concerning employee motivation and organizational performance may be advanced. To advance current thinking, researchers propose a set-theoretic approach to leverage employee motivation for organizational performance.

Radakovich (2016) conducted a study entitled "The Relationship between Organizational Culture, Intrinsic Motivation, and Employee Performance: A Systematic Review and Meta-analysis." This study aimed to explore the relationship between specific

organizational cultural factors (autonomy and meaningful work), intrinsic motivation, and employee performance through a systematic review and meta-analysis. Three separate studies were performed, one for each predictor variable: autonomy, meaningful work, and organizational culture/climate. The first study concluded that autonomy is a predictor of performance; this relationship is partially mediated through intrinsic motivation. The second study concluded that meaningful work is a predictor of performance. The third study was conducted for comparative purposes only and no solid conclusions could be drawn from this study.

In the study done by van der Hoek et al. (2016) on “Goal Setting in Teams: Goal Clarity and Team Performance in the Public Sector”, they found out that with the rise of performance management, work in the public sector has changed. An output focus has become more common. Other changes include decentralization and managing organizations more horizontally. Setting performance goals and working in teams exemplify these developments. Despite extensive literature on goal setting, research on goal setting in teams and empirical studies in public organizations have been largely absent. This study contributes to the fields of public management and teamwork by examining whether and under what team conditions clear goals contribute to team performance and commitment in the Dutch public sector. Analyses on survey data (n = 105 teams) show that both goal clarity and self-management positively affect team performance. The present analyses have shown that clear team goals are important for team performance. It is, therefore, beneficial for teams to make an effort to clarify their goals and create a good common understanding of them.

Santos (2015), in his study entitled “Mentoring, job satisfaction, job dissatisfaction, and organizational commitment among Graduate nurses,” concluded that professional status (a component of job satisfaction) and pay and administration (a component of job dissatisfaction) had the largest impact on determining the nurses’ organizational commitment. The study found that job satisfaction and job dissatisfaction were mediated by mentoring, which in turn influenced organizational commitment.

Rusu and Avasilcai (2014) in the study entitled, “Linking Human Resources Motivation to Organizational Climate” emphasized that motivation has a central role in achieving high performances within organizations. As the organizational climate can be closely correlated with employees’ motivation, providing a motivating environment in industrial

firms depends on managers' ability to create a supportive organizational climate. The main objective of this paper is to underline the most relevant dimensions of the organizational climate that increase employees' intrinsic and extrinsic motivation, according to Herzberg's dual factors theory. By analyzing the relationships between organizational climate dimensions and motivation, the results demonstrated the influence of organizational climate on the level of employees' motivation.

Meade (2013) conducted a study entitled, "Developing a change management plan for organizational transformation." As findings revealed, strategic planning and the establishment of quality objectives are the underpinnings for transformational change management. In today's organizational setting demonstrating the ability to change effectively and efficiently is essential for organizational success. Transformational change requires executive sponsorship, the ability to establish and communicate a strategic vision for the change initiative, and the selection of credible team members from the organization, who can influence stakeholders and engage and guide the organization through the change itself. The focal point of this research is the application and coupling of "The Eight-Stage Process to Create Major Change," established by John P. Kotter, and the "Prosci® ADKAR® (Awareness, Desire, Knowledge, Ability, Reinforcement) model, which acknowledges the people side of change. Through examination and review of the research results, it becomes evident that both models, when combined, provide a comprehensive and repeatable framework from which to drive organizational change and transformation.

Pinkney (2013) conducted a study entitled "Healthcare Reform: Innovative and other proven strategies for successfully managing and implementing organizational change." The study was done in order to qualify innovative and other proven change strategies that assist the healthcare industry and healthcare organizations with implementing organizational change. Accordingly, evidence shows that healthcare spending in the United States grew ten times the base rate in 1980 from \$256 billion to \$2.6 trillion in 2010. Compounding this problem is the limited availability to patient care and the diminishing value of care in many hospitals. The US healthcare industry cannot survive under these circumstances without changing the overall system. In order for healthcare organizations to survive, they must embrace innovative and other proven strategies to remain competitive. The study identified change strategies for healthcare organizations and the healthcare industry to utilize in order to manage organizational change

adequately. The dissertation concluded with strategies such as information technology, the use of incentives, and best practices. These strategies will assist healthcare organizations when undergoing organizational change, and they may serve to lessen the burden of healthcare costs, increase accessibility to care, and provide better quality healthcare.

Raab (2013), in his study entitled, “Developing integrated Change processes: Increasing Efficiency in Change Management Initiative,” concluded that change management and project management are becoming a vital and integrated part of organizations in order to stay viable and maintain a competitive advantage. However, some organizations still do not use a change management process or have a process that does not allow the organization to operate at a high efficiency. The study examined project management and organization development practices to determine if current theories can be integrated and adapted for small, public, information technology (IT) organizations. Based on the information reviewed, a model was developed that organizations can utilize to instigate change with a holistic view, incorporating procedural project management processes with psychological organization development processes.

In another study by Steiger (2013) entitled, “An examination of the influence of organizational structure types and management levels on knowledge management practices in organizations,” the difference between organizational structure types and management levels in terms of perceived levels of knowledge management practices within organizations were analyzed. In San Diego County, data were collected from a sample of 155 individuals employed. Results showed that the knowledge management practices of knowledge transfer, information filtering, and knowledge culture are influenced by organizational structure type. Hence, the researcher concluded that a need exists for management to analyze the structure of its organization to identify opportunities for maximizing efforts related to knowledge management practices. The matrix organizational structure type returned the highest perceived levels of knowledge transfer, information filtering, and knowledge culture, relative to the other organizational structure types. The matrix organizational structure type is heavily associated with the freedom and need to share knowledge. Further, collaboration is a requirement inside a matrix organization, and mutual adjustment is its primary coordinating mechanism. These characteristics of the matrix organizational structure type contribute toward the results that indicate the matrix organizational structure type cultivates the highest perceived

levels of the aforementioned knowledge management practices, relative to the other organizational structure types.

Zeffane et al. (2011), in their study entitled “Communication, Commitment & Trust: Exploring the Triad,” argued that despite growing interest in the issues of communication, trust, and commitment, studies examining the interplay between all of these three variables are lacking. This paper attempts to address this gap. It draws on survey data involving 244 employees from a medium-sized food processing organization operating in NSW (Australia). The study explored relationships between communication, trust, and commitment. Trust was measured by a six-item composite scale assessing overall beliefs in good intentions of organization participants as well as the degree of faith/trust in various actors in the organization, including co-workers and managers at various levels of the hierarchy. Correlation analysis revealed that perceived effectiveness of communication between management and employees, commitment, pride in working for the company, and trust were significantly interrelated. However, the relationship between Trust and Communication was the strongest, with commitment also showing a significant relation to Trust. On the other hand, the relationship between commitment and communication was relatively weaker. The results demonstrate the importance of effective communication within organizations as it relates to trust and organizational commitment. In particular, the study shows that trust and commitment do not just happen; they are forged and maintained through effective communication. Implications for management practice and future research are discussed.

Synthesis

In summary, the reviewed literature and studies focused on the importance of many factors that could contribute to nurses’ commitment, underlining the most relevant dimensions of organizational strategies, change management practices, and motivation. A number of studies that measured commitment had merely used miscellaneous instruments that measured a range of other concepts of worker commitment. Further, to improve the delivery quality of care, nurses should be the focus of attention in the management of human resources in the field of health care. There were institutions that have been targeted in studies regarding nurses’ commitment. Such institutions include private and public hospitals, health care organizations, academe, and clinics. Highlighting the research outcomes from the sampled studies, it clearly shows that commitment was

very instrumental in the manner through which it influences retention, patient satisfaction, organizational turnover, job satisfaction, increasing efficiency, and business viability of the organization. Among the most prominent recommendations in many literature reviews was the need for strategic planning, mentoring, leadership and managerial style, human resource management practices, communication, teamwork and employee engagement with a clear focus on meeting the demand for a healthy environment for work.

Providing quality nursing care to patients was the primary concern of nurses, specifically in all government and private hospitals. Further, the commitment of nurses in Sarangani Province and General Santos City can be influenced by varying factors, including organizational strategies, change management practices, and motivation. The reviewed studies contributed to formulating a development plan for nurses in the hospital and other healthcare settings. For this purpose, the study was conducted.

Research Questions

This study aimed to determine the extent of nurses' commitment in Sarangani Province and General Santos City as influenced by organizational strategies, change management practices, and motivation to present proposals for a development program. Specifically, it answered the following questions:

1. To what extent are the implementation of organizational strategies in the organization in terms of:
 - 1.1 goal setting and visioning;
 - 1.2 human resource management practices;
 - 1.3 operational excellence; and
 - 1.4 corporate culture?
2. To what extent are the implementation of change management practices in terms of:
 - 2.1 leadership;
 - 2.2 communication; and
 - 2.3 development programs?
3. What is the level of motivation in terms of:
 - 3.1 work environment;
 - 3.2 compensation;

- 3.3 promotion and rewards; and
- 3.4 resources?
- 4. What is the level of commitment in terms of:
 - 4.1 employee engagement;
 - 4.2 job satisfaction; and
 - 4.3 career development?
- 5. Is there a significant relationship between the following:
 - 5.1 organizational strategies and commitment;
 - 5.2 change management practices and commitment; and
 - 5.3 motivation and commitment?
- 6. Is there a significant effect of organizational strategies, change management practices, and motivation on nurses' commitment?
- 7. Based on the findings of the study, what development program can be developed?

METHODOLOGY

Respondents of the Study

The respondents of the study were nurses of the identified Department of Health (DOH) accredited hospitals in Sarangani Province and General Santos City. They were those who were currently employed in the hospital for one year and above. They were chosen since they have direct knowledge of the organization's operations. The Hospital Administrators, Human Resource Management and Development Officers, and Chief Nurses served as the key informant interviewees during the cross-validation process. The respondents were asked to answer the items included in the survey questionnaire, while the selected key informants answered questions during the interview. In deciding the sample size of this study, the researcher used Cochran's sample size formula. The Cochran formula allowed the researcher to calculate an ideal sample size given a desired precision level, confidence level, and the estimated proportion of the attribute present in the population. Cochran's formula was considered suited to situations with large populations (Cochran, 1977). In this case, there was no need for 'correction' since the number given by Cochran's formula was lower than the population in this study which was 625 nurses. The researcher set p at 0.05 for this analysis and needed 95 percent confidence and at least five (5) percent accuracy, plus or minus. A 95 percent confidence

rating gave 1.96 values for researcher Z. The researcher then obtained $((1.96)^2 (0.5) (0.5)) / (0.5)^2 = 385$. In order to give the researcher confidence levels, a random sample size of 385 respondents was sufficient. In addition, the researcher used proportionate stratification in order to get the sample size by hospital. This random sampling approach warranted that each hospital is sufficiently distributed within the study's entire sample population. The proportionate stratified random sample was obtained using the formula: $(\text{sample size}/\text{population size}) \times \text{stratum} = \text{size or number of nurses per hospital in this study}$.

Research Instrument

This study utilized a survey questionnaire and an interview guide in data gathering. The Survey Questionnaire was the primary instrument in data gathering, which was developed by the researcher. It was based on the gathered theories and reviewed related literature and studies of the subject of the study. Additionally, it was reviewed, validated, and improved after checking and approval of the research adviser, dissertation panel members, and five expert validators. The questionnaire was rated based on a series of criteria. The key Informant Interview (KII) guide was considered to support the responses generated from the survey questionnaire. The questionnaire was divided into four (4) parts. The first part of the questionnaire evaluated the extent of organizational strategies in terms of goal setting and visioning, human resource management practices, operational excellence, and corporate cultures. The second part determined the extent of change management practices regarding leadership, communication, and quality programs. The third part looked into the level of motivation in terms of work environment, compensation, promotion and rewards, and resources. The fourth part examined nurses' commitment levels regarding employee engagement, job satisfaction, and career development. For the qualitative part of the study, KII was used. It was developed and validated. It contained a list of questions focusing on organizational strategies, change management practices, motivation, and commitment.

Data Gathering Procedure

Before administering the survey questionnaire, the following procedures were observed. Permission was sought from the Chief of Hospital and Hospital Administrator in identified DOH-accredited hospitals of Sarangani Province and General Santos City through a

letter. When approval was given, the validated survey questionnaire was administered to the nurses and the researcher conducted the Key Informant Interviews (KII). A cover letter and the verified survey questionnaire were distributed to the respondents. The survey questionnaires were retrieved after three (3) days from the date these were distributed to give ample time for respondents to answer critically. The Key Informant Interview (KII) was used to triangulate the data obtained based on the findings of the survey questionnaire. The KII's rigors, protocol, and ethics were guaranteed to the respondents from the identified hospitals.

Data Analysis and Interpretation

This study utilized different strategies and methods to interpret the data. These techniques included using mean, spearman's correlation, stepwise linear regression, and multiple linear regression. The mean was used to measure the central tendencies of the gathered data, which helped explain the extent of Organizational Strategies, Change Management Practices, Motivation, and Commitment. Spearman's correlation coefficient was utilized to measure the strength and direction of the variables. This was used to determine the relationships between the independent variables, namely, organizational strategies, change management practices, and motivation, and the dependent variable (i.e., commitment). The following scoring guide was used to evaluate the extent of organizational strategies, change management practices, and nurses' motivation and commitment.

Multiple Linear Regression was used to determine the value of the dependent variable (i.e., commitment) using the independent variables (i.e., organizational strategies, change management practices, and motivation). It was used in this study in order to determine the overall fit of the model and the relative contribution of each of the predictors to the total variance explained. Key informants were interviewed to supplement the data gathered from the survey questionnaires, which enriched the interpretations of the study's findings.

Box 1

Scoring Guide, Description in Determining the Extent and Level of Organizational Strategies, Change Management Practices, Motivation and Commitment

Mean Range	Status	Description
4.21 – 5.00	Very Highly Extensive	Excellent degree to which basic measure of organizational strategies, change management practices, motivation and commitment was observed.
3.41 – 4.20	Highly Extensive	The high degree to which specific measure of organizational strategies, change management practices, motivation and commitment was detected.
2.61 – 3.40	Moderately Extensive	The average degree to which basic measure of organizational strategies, change management practices, motivation and commitment was observed.
1.81 – 2.60	Less Extensive	A specific indicator of organizational strategies, change management practices, motivation and commitment is noted low.
1.00 – 1.80	Least Extensive	A specific indicator of organizational strategies, change management practices, motivation and commitment was observed very little.

Ethical Considerations

This study involved respondents employed in DOH-accredited hospitals in Sarangani Province and General Santos City. As respondents were approached, a verbal explanation of the purpose, duration, possible benefits, and burden of participating in the study was provided. All these were detailed on an information sheet. Respondents were advised that the written and signed consent is not a contract. They were made aware that inclusion is voluntary and they are free to withdraw at any time. All respondents' identity and privacy were protected. Anonymity was maintained, and all paper data were destroyed after transferring to a password-protected database that was accessible only to the researcher and the statistician. The research paradigm did not require withholding any information about the study. As the respondents completed the survey questionnaire, they were informed that they could contact the researcher anytime for questions and

clarification. Throughout the duration of the study, participants were allowed to request and be provided with ongoing information and final results.

Scope and Delimitation

This study focused on the influence of organizational strategies, change management practices, and motivation on nurses' commitment in Sarangani Province and General Santos City. This research covered organizational strategies, change management practices, and motivation as independent variables of the study and nurses' commitment as the dependent variable. The study covered hospitals accredited by the Department of Health (DOH) in Sarangani Province and General Santos City. This study was limited to including randomly sampled nurses from these hospitals. The study was conducted from December 2021 to February 2022. It presented only concepts based on the data gathered from the respondents through an answered survey questionnaire and from the key informant interview. Further, the influence of organizational strategies, change management practices, and motivation on nurses' commitment was determined using Spearman's correlation and multiple linear regression.

RESULTS

Extent of Implementation of Organizational Strategies in the Organization

The data presented in Table 1 pertain to the extent to which organizational strategies, such as goal setting and visioning, human resource management practices, operational excellence, and corporate culture, have been implemented.

Table 1

Extent of Implementation of Organizational Strategies in the Organization

Parameters	Mean Value	Description
1. Goal setting and visioning	4.18	Highly Extensive
2. Human resource management practices	4.22	Very Highly Extensive
3. Operational excellence	4.06	Highly Extensive

4. Corporate culture	4.43	Very Highly Extensive
Grand Mean	4.22	Very Highly Extensive

Goal Setting and Visioning

Goal setting and visioning have a statistical value mean of 4.18. The mean value denoted “highly extensive.” Nurses believe that the organization has a clear plan, vision, and set of direction in place to achieve the various organizational goals and objectives.

Human Resource Management Practices

The mean level value of human resource management practices is 4.22, which is interpreted as “very highly extensive.” Human resource management practices were visible in the organization. During the Key Informant Interview, participants claimed that the hospital and human resource management offices have established and promoted decent work and growth.

Operational excellence

Results revealed that the mean value of 4.06 for operational excellence is assessed as “highly extensive.” Based on the data, nurses believed that hospital management implemented strategies to ensure a safe work environment and quality hospital operations, especially during this pandemic.

Corporate culture

Table 1 in the previous section presented that corporate culture has a statistical mean value of 4.43 and was interpreted as “very highly extensive.” Corporate culture was strongly evident in the hospitals of Sarangani Province and General Santos City. Nurses believed that the hospital organization maintained activities, values, and beliefs that are widely shared and strongly held throughout the organization.

Extent of Implementation of Change Management Practices in the organization

Table 2 presented the extent of implementation of change management practices in hospitals of Sarangani Province and General Santos City regarding leadership, communication, and development programs.

Table 2

Extent of Implementation of Change Management Practices in the organization

Parameters	Mean Value	Description
1. Leadership	4.21	Very Highly Extensive
2. Communication	3.57	Highly Extensive
3. Development Programs	4.01	Highly Extensive
Grand Mean	3.93	Highly Extensive

Leadership

The mean score presented in Table 2 for leadership as an indicator of change management practices is 4.21, which is assessed as “very highly extensive.” Based on the data, nurses believe that hospital leaders are committed to the change process and use different strategies during the change process. In the key informant interview (KII) conducted, some participants stated that leaders of the organization should take the driver's seat in institutionalizing change, and it should create a ripple effect on employees in order to achieve organizational goals. As experienced, when employees hear, see, and feel the positive outcome of change from the management, they get involved. Further, one participant said that change is part of any hospital organization. Growth is important for us to deliver quality hospital care, and if our employees are well informed and educated by the management, employees commit to the planned change. Another participant said that, when there are management practices being planned, the staff's welfare is also considered before implementing it.

Communication

The mean level value of communication is 3.57, which is interpreted as “highly extensive.” The hospital organization's communication flow during a change process was visible, just

as it was with leadership. In fact, it surfaced during the KII, as one respondent claimed that during a planned change, the respective department heads and management actively involved employees in the process and utilized various communication strategies.

Development Programs

Development programs received a mean value of 4.01, which is described as “highly extensive.” This demonstrated that the organizations have programs designed to improve nurses’ skills, knowledge, and attitudes during the change process, boosting nurses’ commitment to hospitals.

Level of Motivation

This section discussed nurses’ motivation level regarding work environment, compensation, promotion, and rewards and resources, as presented in Table 3.

Work Environment

Work environment gets a mean of 4.24 which is interpreted as “very highly extensive”. This meant that the hospitals in Sarangani Province and General Santos City had a positive work environment that promoted employee well-being, productivity, support, and growth. The Key Informant Interview (KII) results showed that nurses were motivated to work in a supportive, satisfying, and empowering environment with a culture of continuous improvement and teamwork.

Compensation

Table 3 showed the mean of 3.89 for compensation, interpreted as “highly extensive.” The results showed that nurses are aware of the hospital's salary structure and compensation policy and agree that they are fairly compensated. A participating nurse said, “Although the salary is not too good, I am satisfied with my nursing job because people in our hospital give me a lot of respect.” (A5, L255-257) Another participant said, “I think one factor that mainly makes me satisfied with this nursing profession is the love to care for patients and not merely the salary.” (A7, L268-269) As expressed by one of the participants, even though the salary received by nurses was not very attractive, some

nurses are satisfied with the nursing job because of the positive contributions and differences they make in the lives of the patients on a daily basis. The respondents opined that training and promotions, availability of medical equipment and suppliers, prestige, big pay, and bonuses are specific factors that prevented turnover and improved job satisfaction. The participants argued that employee respect, competitive pay, recognition, love, and promotion were essential psychological needs and intrinsic factors necessary for high job satisfaction.

Table 3
Level of Motivation

Parameters	Mean Value	Description
1. Work Environment	4.24	Very Highly Extensive
2. Compensation	3.89	Highly Extensive
3. Promotion and Rewards	3.88	Highly Extensive
4. Resources	3.76	Highly Extensive
Grand Mean	3.94	Highly Extensive

Promotion and Rewards

The mean level of promotion and rewards is 3.88, which is interpreted as “highly extensive.” This mean value denotes that nurses are aware of the organization's appraisal system.

Resources

In Table 3, the mean score of resources is 3.76, which is interpreted as “highly extensive.” This implies that nurses believed that the organization provided training, key performance measures, and equipment, supplies, and resources necessary for nurses to perform their duties.

Level of Commitment

Table 4 showed the indicators of commitment: employee engagement, job satisfaction, and career development. The weighted mean was used to describe the results of the study.

Table 4
Level of Commitment

Parameters	Mean Value	Description
1. Employee Engagement	4.43	Very Highly Extensive
2. Job Satisfaction	4.22	Very Highly Extensive
3. Career Development	4.46	Very Highly Extensive
Grand Mean	4.37	Very Highly Extensive

Employee Engagement

The mean score for employee engagement is 4.31, interpreted as “very highly extensive.” Results from KII showed that nurses’ understanding of their work and responsibilities and their capacity to respond to designated assignments were proportionate with the completion of assigned tasks. Employees who are engaged and committed to the organization and its goal care about the hospital, their team, and their patients. There was a significant link between employee engagement and patient care and satisfaction improvements. Employee engagement was strongly evident in the hospital organization, where nurses showed strong commitment to work, tasks, and responsibilities.

Job Satisfaction

Based on the result shown in Table 4, the statistical mean of job satisfaction is 4.22. The mean value is interpreted as “very highly extensive.” The data showed that individuals who form many positive relationships with their peers, supervisors, and the workplace become more committed, which positively influences job satisfaction.

Career Development

The mean value for career development is 4.46, which is interpreted as “very highly extensive.” The results showed that nurses believed that programs and activities were conducted in the organization to ensure personnel improvement. The findings supported the prior research findings of the positive relationship between organizational support and career development.

Relationship between Organizational Strategies and Commitment

Table 5

Relationship between Organizational Strategies and Commitment

Correlations			Organizational Strategies	Commitment
	Pearson Correlation		1	.355**
Organizational Strategies	Sig. (2-tailed)			.000
Spearman's rho	N		344	344
	Pearson Correlation		.355**	1
Commitment	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000	
	N		344	344

Table 5 presents the relationship between organizational strategies and commitment. Spearman’s Correlation Coefficient was utilized in order to establish the relationship between organizational strategies and commitment. The correlation results showed a significantly low positive correlation $r = 0.355$ ($\text{sig.} = 0.000$) between organizational strategies and commitment. This positive correlation meant that organizational strategies are directly proportional to commitment. The higher the implementation of organizational strategies, the commitment of nurses is also high. However, when there is low implementation of organizational strategies, the commitment of nurses will also be low. Hence, the null hypothesis (H_{01}), which stated that there is no significant relationship between organizational strategies and nurses’ commitment, is rejected. Thus, there is evidence that there is a significant relationship between organizational strategies and

commitment. The emphasis is certainly on commitment and the willingness and determination on the part of management. When the entire organization is committed to the same mission, goals, and objectives, then there is an effective organization.

Relationship between Change Management Practices and Commitment

Table 6 presents the result of the relationship between change management practices and commitment. The correlation between change management practices and commitment is significantly very low positive, with a correlation value of $r = 0.164$ ($\text{sig.} = 0.002$). The positive correlation between change management practices and commitment signified that the higher the change management practices in hospitals of Sarangani Province and General Santos City, the higher the commitment of nurses.

Table 6

Relationship between Change Management Practices and Commitment

				Correlations	
				Change Management Practices	Commitment
	Change Management Practices	Management	Pearson Correlation	1	.164**
			Sig. (2-tailed)		.002
Spearman's rho			N	344	344
			Pearson Correlation	.164**	1
	Commitment		Sig. (2-tailed)	.002	
			N	344	344

This finding was supported by the statements of the participants during the KII wherein the participants mentioned that organizations conduct consultations and mentoring programs during the change process. However, some participants mentioned that some organizations also failed to inform nurses on the change process. The null hypothesis, which stated that (H_02) there is no significant relationship between change management practices and nurses' commitment, is rejected.

Relationship between Motivation and Commitment

Results using SPSS about the relationship between motivation and commitment

Table 7
Relationship between Motivation and Commitment

			Motivation	Commitment
Spearman's rho		Correlation Coefficient	1.000	.214**
	Motivation	Sig. (2-tailed)	.	.000
		N	344	344
		Correlation Coefficient	.214**	1.000
	Commitment	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.
		N	344	344

are shown in Table 7. The correlation test results showed a significantly low positive correlation between motivation and commitment with an r-value of .214 (sig.=0.000). This positive correlation may indicate that motivation would result in positive commitment of nurses although the significance is low. Although the significance is low, there is still a significant relationship between the two variables. The positive correlation can be attributed to the various practices of hospital organizations in Sarangani Province and General Santos City, wherein the management has provided a safe working environment, adequate pay, rewards, and resources, as mentioned during the Key Informant Interview. Therefore, the null hypothesis (Ho3), which states that there is no significant relationship between motivation and commitment, is rejected. Thus, there is a shred of evidence that there is a significant relationship between motivation and commitment.

Effects of Organizational Strategies, Change Management Practices, and Motivation on Commitment

Multiple linear regression was utilized to determine which organizational strategies, change management practices, and motivation significantly affect commitment.

Table 8

Effects of Organizational Strategies, Change Management Practices and Motivation on Commitment

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.353 ^a	.125	.098	.26586

a. Predictors: (Constant), Organizational Strategies, Motivation, Change Management Practices

Organizational strategies, change management practices, and motivation showed a weak Pearson correlation of .353. Further, the coefficient of determination R^2 of 12.5 is also weak because this means that 87.5% of the changes in commitment may be explained by factors other than organizational strategies, change management practices, and motivation. Participants during the KII also shared that family and community support were important factors in determining nurses' commitment. Further, according to a Chief Nurse, commitment gained greater importance during the crisis, and factors such as burnout, sense of value, degree of freedom and autonomy, feedback mechanism, patient satisfaction, professional ethics, attitude, and nursing empowerment can be determinants of the nurse's level of commitment. Hence, the null hypothesis (H_{04}), which stated that there is no significant effect of organizational strategies, change management practices, and motivation on nurses' commitment, is rejected. This study significantly affects organizational strategies, change management practices, and motivation on nurses' commitment. In summary, all of the variables showed a significant effect on nurses' commitment. Further, the research was delimited to Sarangani Province and General Santos City hospitals. Organizations such as hospitals face new challenges in creating a

committed workforce. However, commitment was ensured with the right organizational strategies, change management practices, and motivational factors.

DISCUSSION

This chapter summarizes the findings on the extent of implementation of organizational strategies, the extent of implementation of change management practices, the level of motivation and commitment of nurses in Sarangani Province and General Santos City, and which variable significantly affects commitment. The findings and recommendations are also presented.

The following were the findings of the study:

In terms of the extent of implementation of organizational strategies, corporate culture got the highest grand mean of 4.43, followed by human resource management practices with a grand mean of 4.22, then goal setting and visioning with a grand mean of 4.18, and lastly, operational excellence at 4.06. All were rated as very highly extensive and highly extensive, respectively, which meant that these measures were detected at a high degree.

This implied that hospitals in Sarangani Province and General Santos City have a dynamic long-term plan and have implemented a sum of actions, strategies, and activities in terms of human resource management and operation and developed a culture towards the realization of the organization's goals. Further, participants during the KII spoke about leadership frequently in interviews. There were several notations reflective of leadership's impact on organizational strategies. Some participants included statements that the goal of the organization is to be a leader in healthcare, and this was evident in terms of the expressed desires of participants to partake in interviews and continue to learn effective organizational strategies through the results of this study.

In terms of the extent of implementation of change management practices, leadership got the highest grand mean of 4.21, followed by development programs at 4.01, and lastly, communication with a grand mean of 3.57. All measures were detected at a high degree.

To sum up, the statistical grand mean for the extent of implementation of change management practices is 3.93, which is interpreted as “highly extensive.” This implies that the hospitals promote and implement different approaches, including leadership support, open communication, and development programs, to transition or transform an organization's goals, processes, or technologies.

In terms of the level of motivation, all were rated as very highly extensive and highly extensive, respectively, which means these measures were detected at a high degree. Work environment got the highest grand mean of 4.24, followed by compensation with a grand mean of 3.89, promotion and rewards with a grand mean of 3.88, and resources with a grand mean of 3.76. In summary, data showed that all indicators were being observed extensively, with a grand mean of 3.94. This meant that there was a high degree to which the indicators were being detected. It implied that nurses' motivation is equally important in promoting commitment. Despite some studies supporting the claim that nurses are satisfied with their jobs, migration and turnover rates of nurses are still high. Filipino nurses continuously migrating to other countries have endangered the Philippines' quality of patient care services.

In terms of the level of commitment, career development got the highest grand mean of 4.46 followed by employee engagement with a grand mean of 4.43 and job satisfaction with a grand mean of 4.22. To sum up, the level of commitment, the statistical grand mean was 4.37, which was interpreted as “very highly extensive.” It implied that nurses were committed in terms of employee engagement, job satisfaction, and career development. It also showed that leadership behaviors and the role of the management have often been seen as a vital element that influences the level of commitment of employees within the organization to achieve the organizational objectives.

Among the identified variables, organizational strategies ($r=0.355$) ($\text{sig}=0.000$), change management practices with a correlation value of $r = 0.164$ ($\text{sig.}=0.002$), and motivation ($r=\text{value of } .214$ ($\text{sig.}=0.000$)) showed significant relationships with commitment.

Finally, when loaded together, all independent variables, namely, organizational strategies, change management practices, and motivation with an r-square value gave an amount of 12.5% ($p<.005$) and significantly affected commitment.

A development program was formulated incorporating organizational strategies, change management practices, and motivation which are the activities that influenced nurses' commitment.

Conclusions

The study's findings led to the following conclusions: Hospital organizations were implementing organizational strategies in terms of goal setting and visioning, human resource management practices, operational excellence, and corporate culture to a high degree. Hospital organizations were executing change management practices in terms of leadership, communication, and development programs to a high degree.

Hospital organizations were promoting programs on motivation in terms of work environment, compensation, promotion and rewards, and resources to a high degree. The level of nurses commitment in terms of employee engagement, job satisfaction and career development was at a high degree. The work of being a nurse or the mission itself appears to be where most of the nurses' commitment comes from. This may explain why nurses still find nursing a fulfilling, rewarding, and satisfying profession.

All identified variables significantly influenced nurses' commitment, namely organizational strategies, change management practices, and motivation. A development program is formulated to promote and strengthen nurses' commitment in Sarangani Province and General Santos City.

Recommendations

The study's findings revealed significant relationships among organizational strategies, change management practices, and motivation and nurses' commitment.

As a result, the following suggestions were made. Hospital executives may consider strengthening organizational strategy programs focusing on strategic planning and management to address the low relationship between organizational strategies and

commitment. Strategic planning of organizations positively affects personnel commitment.

Hospital executives, human resource management officers, and chief nurses shall participate nurses in managerial decision-making, use improved communication skills, and give appreciation for their contributions to the organization. Chief nurses need to include an array of activities in change management practices, such as leadership alignment, holistic communication planning, and organizational development through workshops and seminars to increase the low relationship between change management practices and commitment. Change management that is based on communication and employee participation will enhance employees' commitment to the organization.

Human resource management officers should provide a series of orientation sessions and mentoring programs on the change management process to make nurses aware of new hospital policies and nursing practices. This will provide support and guidance to facilitate a successful transition. Policymakers may consider improving the practice of the factors in motivation, focusing on workplace safety, compensation, promotion, and rewards and resources. Employees who are motivated and have a positive attitude are more committed.

Hospital executives and human resource management officers shall implement programs through seminar workshops on employee engagement, job satisfaction, and career development to strengthen nurses' commitment.

Nurses shall participate in programs and activities related to strengthening organizational strategies, change management practices, and motivation to ensure commitment. Future researchers may replicate and use the findings of this study as baseline information in exploring other factors that will constitute 87.5% of organizational strategies, change management practices, and motivation. Future researchers may look for and include

more variables and domains or aspects of work better to understand the sources of nurses' level of commitment.

A proposed development program was recommended for implementation, which is relevant and timely in addressing the concern about increasing nurses' commitment.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

This study involved respondents employed in DOH-accredited hospitals in Sarangani Province and General Santos City. As respondents were approached, a verbal explanation of the purpose, duration, possible benefits, and burden of participating in the study was provided. All these were detailed on an information sheet. Respondents were advised that the written and signed consent is not a contract. They were made aware that inclusion is voluntary and they are free to withdraw at any time. All respondents' identity and privacy were protected. Anonymity was maintained, and all paper data were destroyed after transferring to a password-protected database that was accessible only to the researcher and the statistician. The research paradigm did not require withholding any information about the study. As the respondents completed the survey questionnaire, they were informed that they could contact the researcher anytime for questions and clarification. Throughout the duration of the study, participants were allowed to request and be provided with ongoing information and final results.

Acknowledgments

The author is very grateful to GOD ALMIGHTY, for this study would not have been possible without His grace and blessings. I'd like to express my immeasurable appreciation and deepest gratitude to the following persons who, in one way or another, have contributed to making this study possible. To my dear mother Mary Ann L. Baculio and grandparents Teresita Q. Lubaton, Rufoldo Lubaton, and Maria Ofelia L. Baculio, I want to express my heartfelt gratitude for being my prayer warriors. I owe my deepest gratitude to my family for their endless support for this scholarly endeavor and to my brothers, Kevin, Irvin, Kobe, Lebrone, and Earl, for being a constant source of joy through the challenges of this dissertation. To Dr. Joanne J. Java, CPA, for her motivation, patience, and immense knowledge throughout the crucial steps of the research process. Her guidance helped me throughout the research and writing of this dissertation. To. Dr.

Aflie Marie R. Custodio, DM, Program Chair, Dr. Estela Marie Verana, and Dr. Olivia Sudaria for their encouragement and insightful comments. Their endless guidance is hard to forget throughout my life. To Dr. Gina A. De Guzman, CE, Dean of the Graduate School, for her words of encouragement. To Dr. Gaudy Ortizo, OIC/Dean of the Graduate School, for his untiring support and patience in critiquing this dissertation. To Dr. Rogen Doronila, my statistician for sharing his knowledge in the analysis of data and its statistical computations. To Dr. Edgar B. Manubag, CE, for his valuable comments and suggestions that benefited the success of this study. His words of hope and encouragements were extremely invaluable, especially during the seemingly challenging times. To my DM family, namely, Dr. Lubon, Dr. Estorninos, Dr. Guevarra and Dr. Sanido, for their constant support and help. I would like to express profound gratitude to my nursing colleagues, chief nurses, chief of hospital, medical directors, administrative officers and human resource management officers who I am honored to work with and who all enthusiastically participated in the study. To my Provincial Local Government Unit of Sarangani, Sarangani Provincial Hospital - Malungon, Sarangani Provincial Employees Union, General Santos Doctors' Medical School Foundation, Incorporated, Brokenshire College of Socsargen, family and friends, for their relentless encouragement and optimism. From the bottom of my heart, thank you! Lastly, this is dedicated to all nurses for serving with care, compassion, and commitment to putting the interests of others before their own and those of their families.

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